

Determinants of Risky Sexual Behaviours Among Adolescent Girls Attending Babcock University High School, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State

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Abstract:

Risky sexual behaviours have been identified to be on the increase among female adolescent and some factors have been found to be a determinant of these risky sexual behaviours. This study was carried out to examine the determinants of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun state. Descriptive research design was adopted for this study and simple random method was used to select 271 female adolescent students from Babcock university high school Ilishan Remo Ogun state. The researcher designed questionnaire was used to collect data from the students. Face and content validity of instrument was ascertained by experts of Nursing Sciences and Tests and Measurement. Reliability was determined using internal consistency method and Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was 0.81. Three research questions were answered using descriptive statistics while three hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlations. The findings of the study revealed that majority of the respondents had high knowledge (72.5%) and perception (62.7%) of risky sexual behaviour. The study also found that there is significant relationship between the knowledge, attitude, perception and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls. It was recommended among others that there is need for teachers and

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parents to properly educate and inform students on the issue of risky sexual behaviour in schools and at home so as to eliminate wrong perceptions and attitudes towards the subject.

Keywords: Adolescent Girls, Determinants, Risky Sexual Behaviour,

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Introduction

Adolescents are known to be an adventurous group, and often engage in risky behaviours such as smoking, drinking alcohol, using drugs, and early unprotected sexual activity. Practices such as homosexuality, lesbianism, and sexual orgies are indulged in just for the reason of experimentation and peer influences, owing to a wealth of uncensored information they are exposed to, through an intensifying wave of westernization, the Internet, and electronic media (Adeyemo & Williams, 2019). Risky sexual behaviour is any behaviour that increases the probability of negative consequences associated with sexual contact, including HIV/AIDS or other sexually transmitted diseases (STD), abortion and unplanned pregnancy. It also includes behaviours like having multiple sexual partners, having risky casual or unknown sexual partners, early sexual initiation and failure to discuss risk topics prior to intercourse and failure to take protective actions, such as use of condoms and birth control (Akpama, 2017).

Factors that predispose to high risk sexual practices are: early sexual debut, cultural practices, drug abuse and illiteracy. The mean age of 15 years for sexual debut has been reported in Nigeria. Religion, government policies, socioeconomic status, place of residence, family, gender, constitute distant conceptual framework on adolescent sexual risk taking in Nigeria while the mass media, communication, peer influence, contraception, and early marriage constitute the proximal factors. Risky sexual behaviours could also be influenced by inter social factors such as emotional intelligence, self-esteem, media and religiosity (Diala, Olujimi, Harris, & Feyisetan, 2017).

The Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey in 2014 reported that the median age at first sexual intercourse for girls is 16 years. By ages 18 and 20, 63% and approximately 80% respectively have experienced sexual intercourse. The overall development of the adolescent is shaped by many factors; however, sexual development is a normal and seemingly vital part of adolescence as it involves not only the physical changes but also the formation of one's individuality, perspective, attitudes, expression of intimacy and the defining experience within sexual and romantic framework (Adeyemo & Williams, 2019).

Risky sexual behaviour is a behaviour related to sexuality which increases the susceptibility of an individual to problems related to sexuality and reproductive health like sexually transmitted disease (STIs), human immune deficiency virus (HIV), unwanted and unplanned pregnancy, abortion, and psychological distress (Fentahun & Mamo, 2017). Risky behaviour includes having more than one sexual partner, early sexual initiation, inconsistent use of condom, and having sex with commercial sex workers (Abebe, Tsion & Netsanet, 2018). Additionally, the use of substances during sex may make young people engage in risky sexual behaviours since it affects their judgment (Woolf-King, Rice, Truong, Woods, Jerome, & Carrico, 2016). Furthermore, negative effects of risky sexual behaviours such as increased prevalence of sexually transmitted infection and unwanted pregnancy has been identified among adolescent girls. The researchers observed that risky sexual behaviours have been on the increase in this part of the society and the effect is seen more in adolescent girls. Because of high rate of illiteracy, parents do not teach their children on the danger of these behaviours especially at the stage of adolescence. The health hazards associated with sexual risk taken among young people are well documented, but little is known about the factors associated

with sexual behaviour among adolescents in Nigeria especially in Ogun State. Hence, this study therefore assesses determinants of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The study specifically examined:

1. the knowledge level of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school;
2. the attitude on risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school; and
3. the perception about risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What is the knowledge level of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State?
2. What is the attitude on risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State?
3. What is the perception about risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between respondent's level of knowledge on risky sexual behaviour and risky sexual behaviours
2. There is no significant relationship between respondent's attitude towards risky sexual behaviour and risky sexual behaviours
3. There is no significant relationship between respondent's perception on risky sexual behaviour and risky sexual behaviour

Methodology

Descriptive research design was used to investigate determinants of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The population for this study were 693 Adolescent female students in Babcock University High school Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The sample size for this study was determined by applying the Cochran (1997) formula as it is the standard method of randomization and is also suitable for identifying the limits of errors considered as the most essential items in the survey. Therefore, sample of 271 female students were selected for the study.

A pretested, self-administered, semi-structured questionnaire was used to obtain data from the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of four sections which were structured to obtain information on the following areas; socio-demographic, respondents knowledge on risky behaviours, respondents attitude on risky behaviours and respondents perception on risky behaviours. The validity of instrument was ascertained by presenting the instrument for the study to experts in the field of Nursing Sciences and Tests and Measurement to ensure face and content validity of the instrument. Reliability of the instrument was done through

internal consistency method using a total of 40 respondents outside the sampled area. Cronbach alpha reliability co-efficient of 0.81 was gotten.

Questionnaires were collected after completion and checked for appropriateness and complete filling. Data collection was done for a period of 1 week. Data was processed and analyzed using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23, frequency tables were made and data was presented on it. Three research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and percentages while three hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson's product moment correlation at 0.01 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the knowledge level of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State?

Table 1: Frequency on Respondents Knowledge on Risky Sexual Behaviours

Category		Respondents 271
		Frequency F (%)
Risky sexual behaviour is any behaviour that increases the probability of negative consequences associated with sexual contact	Yes	162(59.8%)
	No	109 (40.2%)
HIV and STI'S are consequences of engaging in risky sexual behaviours	Yes	154 (56.8%)
	No	(43.2%)
HIV AND STI'S can be passed during sexual intercourse from an infected person to a person who is not infected if a condom is not used.	Yes	167 (61.6%)
	No	104 (38.4%)
Taking alcohol and hard drugs can induce an individual to engage in risky sexual behaviour	Yes	157 (57.9%)
	No	114 (42.1%)
Engaging in unprotected sex (sex with one or more persons whether a stranger or not without the use of a condom or any other form of protection such as pills) is a form of risky sexual behaviour.	Yes	175 (64.6%)
	No	96 (35.4%)
Unwanted pregnancy and abortions are consequences of engaging in risky sexual behaviours.	Yes	182 (67.2%)
	No	89 (32.8%)
Sexual violence or sexual coercion is a form of risky sexual behaviour.	Yes	161 (59.4%)
	No	110 (40.6%)
Early education of adolescents on risky sexual behaviours can	Yes	

reduce the effect of risky sexual behaviours on adolescents and the society at large.		187 (69.0%)
	No	84 (31.0%)
Peer pressure predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours.	Yes	159 (58.7%)
	No	112 (41.3%)
Improper education on the issue of risky sexual behaviour.	Yes	164 (60.5%)
	No	107 (39.5%)
Age of the individual predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours.	Yes	173 (63.8%)
	No	98 (36.2%)
Environment where an individual relates such as school, home, place of worship etc predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours.	Yes	172 (63.5%)
	No	99 (36.5%)
Sexual coercion or violence predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours.	Yes	185 (68.3%)
	No	86 (31.7%)
Social media predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours.	Yes	196 (72.3%)
	No	75 (27.7%)

Table 2: Level of Knowledge On Risky Sexual Behaviours

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
High level of knowledge (76-100)	210	77.5
Average level of knowledge (46-75)	47	17.3
Low level of knowledge (0-45)	14	5.2
Total	271	100.0

Table 1 shows that (59.8%) of the respondents agree that risky sexual behaviour is any behaviour that increases the probability of negative consequences associated with sexual contact while (40.2%) did not agree. The findings also revealed that (56.8%) of the respondents supports that HIV and STI'S are consequences of engaging in risky sexual behaviours while (43.2%) do not it reveals support. The study further found that (61.6%) of the respondents accept that HIV AND STI'S can be passed during sexual intercourse from an infected person to a person who is not infected if a condom is not used while (38.4%) do not accept. The result also reveals that (64.6%) of the respondents accept that engaging in unprotected sex (sex with one or more persons whether a stranger or not without the use of a condom or any other form of protection such as pills) is a form of risky sexual behaviour while (35.4%) do not accept.

The result also shows that (67.2%) of the respondents accept that unwanted pregnancy and abortions are consequences of engaging in risky sexual behaviours while

(32.8%) of the respondents do not accept. The result further reveals that (59.4%) of the respondents accept that sexual violence or sexual coercion is a form of risky sexual behaviour while (40.6%) do not accept that sexual violence or sexual coercion is a form of risky sexual behaviour. The result also reveals that (69%) of the respondents accept that early education of adolescents on risky sexual behaviours can reduce the effect of risky sexual behaviours on adolescents and the society at large while (41%) do not accept. Also the result reveals that peer pressure predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours while (41.3%) do not accept that Peer pressure predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours. The result also depicts that (60.5%) of the respondents accept that improper education on the issue of risky sexual behaviour while (39.5%) of the respondents do not accept that improper education on the issue of risky sexual behaviour.

The result further shows that (63.8%) of the respondents accept that age of the individual predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours while (36.2%) of the respondents do not accept that age of the individual predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours. The result also reveals that (63.5%) of the respondents accept that environment where an individual relates such as school, home, place of worship etc. predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours while (36.5%) of the respondents do not accept. Also the results show that sexual coercion or violence predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours while (31.7%) do not accept. The findings further reveals that (72.3%) of the respondents accept that social media predisposes adolescents to risky sexual behaviours, while about (27.7%) do not accept.

Also result from table 2 shows that about (77.5%) majority of the respondents have high level of knowledge while 22.5% have low level of knowledge.

Research Question 2: What is the attitude on risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State?

Table 3: Frequency on attitude towards risky sexual behaviours

VARIABLE	SA	A	IN	D	SD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
I feel comfortable discussing sex related issues or issues relating to the opposite sex with my parents.	41 (15.1%)	52 (19.2%)	114 (42.1%)	54 (19.9%)	10 (3.7%)
My parents shun me when I try to discuss sex related issues or issues concerning the opposite sex with them.	93(34.3 %)	83(30.6 %)	22(8.1 %)	34 (12.5%)	39(14.4 %)
I don't think engaging in oral sex and anal sex is a form of indulging in risky sexual behaviour.	81 (29.9%)	101(37. 3%)	65(24.0 %)	15 (5.5%)	9 (3.3%)
I think it is appropriate to use condoms during sexual intercourse whether with a	67 (24.7%)	104(38. 4%)	60(22.1 %)	25 (9.2%)	15 (5.5%)

stranger or a usual partner.					
I have been told that I am too young to talk or know about the dangers of risky sexual behaviours.	92 (33.9%)	115(42.4%)	30(11.1%)	20 (7.4%)	14 (5.2%)

Table 4: Level of attitude towards risky sexual behaviours

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Positive Attitude (51-100)	196	72.3
Negative Attitude (0-50)	75	27.7
Total	271	100.0

Results from table 3 shows that (15.1%) of the respondents agree that they feel comfortable discussing sex related issues or issues relating to the opposite sex with their parents, 52(19.2%) strongly agree, (42.1%) were indifferent, (19.9%) disagree and (3.7%) strongly disagree.

The result also shows that (34.3%) agree, (30.6%) strongly agree, (8.1%) were indifferent, (12.5%) disagree and (14.4%) strongly disagree that their parents shun them when they try to discuss sex related issues or issues concerning the opposite sex with them. Furthermore, the result also reveals that (29.9%) of the respondents agree, (37.7%) strongly agree, (24%) were indifferent, (5.5%) disagree and (3.3%) strongly agree that they don't think engaging in oral sex and anal sex is a form of indulging in risky sexual behaviour. Also about (24.7%) the respondents strongly agree that it is appropriate to use condoms during sexual intercourse whether with a stranger or a usual partner, (38.4%) agree, (22.1%) were indifferent, (9.2%) disagree, (5.5%) strongly disagree. The result also shows that (33.9%) of the respondents agree, (42.4%) strongly agree, (11.1%) were indifferent, (7.4%) disagree, (5.2%) strongly disagree that have been told that they are too young to talk or know about the dangers of risky sexual behaviours.

Furthermore, table 4 shows that about (72.3%) of the respondents have positive attitude towards risky sexual behaviours while about (27.7%) have negative attitude.

Research Question 3: What is the perception about risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State?

Table 5: Frequency on perception on risky sexual behaviour

VARIABLE	SA	A	IN	D	SD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
It is a taboo to talk about risky sexual behaviours or other sex related topics in my religion.	68 (25.1%)	82 (30.3%)	81(29.9%)	22 (8.1%)	18 (6.6%)

It is wrong for females to be enlightened on risky sexual behaviours and other sex related issues.	42 (15.5%)	67 (24.7%)	62(2 2.9%)	73 (26.9%)	27(10. 0%)
It is a taboo to talk about risky sexual behaviours or other sex related topics in my school.	88 (32.5%)	118(4 3.5%)	48(1 7.7%)	11 (4.1%)	6 (2.2%)
It is a taboo to talk about risky sexual behaviours or other sex related topics in my culture.	70 (25.8%)	88 (32.5%)	36(1 3.3%)	57 (21.0%)	20 (7.4%)

Table 6: Level of perception towards risky sexual behaviours

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Positive Attitude (51-100)	170	62.7
Negative Attitude (0-50)	101	37.3
Total	271	100.0

Result from table 5 reveals that (25.1%) agree that it is a taboo to talk about risky sexual behaviours or other sex related topics in their religion, about (30.3%) strongly agree, (29.9%) were indifferent, (8.1%) disagree and (6.6%) strongly disagree. The findings also reveals that (15.5%) of the respondents agree that it is wrong for females to be enlightened on risky sexual behaviours and other sex related issues, about (24.7%) strongly agree, (22.9%) were indifferent, (26.9%) disagree and (10%) strongly disagree that it is wrong for females to be enlightened on risky sexual behaviours and other sex related issues. Furthermore, the result reveals that (32.5%) of the respondents agree that it is a taboo to talk about risky sexual behaviours or other sex related topics in their school, (43.5%) strongly agree, (17.7%) were indifferent, (4.1%) disagree and (2.2%) strongly disagree. Also about (25.8%) of the respondents agree that it is a taboo to talk about risky sexual behaviours or other sex related topics in their culture, about (32.5%) strongly agreed, (13.3%) were indifferent, (21%) of the respondents disagreed while (7.4%) strongly disagreed.

Consequently, the result in table 6 shows that about (62.7%) of the respondents have positive perception towards risky sexual behaviours while about (37.3%) of the respondents have negative towards risky sexual behaviours.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between respondent's level of knowledge on risky sexual behaviour and risky sexual behaviours

Table 7: Pearson product moment correlations between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls

	Mean score	SD		knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours	risky sexual behaviours
Knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours	2.6193	0.8550	Pearson Correlation	1	.062**
			Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
			N	271	271
Risky sexual behaviours			Pearson Correlation	.062**	1
			Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
			N	271	271

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Result from table 7 revealed that there is a significant relationship between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The correlation result table revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State ($r=.062$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is hereby rejected. By this it means that there is a significant relationship between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between respondent's attitude towards risky sexual behaviour and risky sexual behaviours

Table 8: Pearson product moment correlations between attitude about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending

	Mean score	SD		Attitude about risky sexual behaviours	Risky sexual behaviours
Attitude about risky sexual behaviours	6.756	0.324	Pearson Correlation	1	.346**
			Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
			N	271	271
Risky sexual behaviours			Pearson Correlation	.346*	1
			Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
			N	271	271

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Result from table 8 above showed that there is a significant relationship between attitude about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The correlation result showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between attitude about risky

sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State ($r=.346$, $p<0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which says that there is no significant relationship between attitude on risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between attitude about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between respondent's perception on risky sexual behaviour and risky sexual behaviour

Table 9: Pearson product moment correlations between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls

	Mean score	SD		Perception about risky sexual behaviours	Risky sexual behaviours
Perception about risky sexual behaviours	7.8686	1.75093	Pearson Correlation	1	.210
			Sig. (2-tailed)		.181
			N	271	271
Risky sexual behaviours			Pearson Correlation	.210	1
			Sig. (2-tailed)	.181	
			N	271	271

Result from table 9 revealed that there is no significant relationship between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The correlation result table above revealed that there is a positive and an insignificant relationship between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. ($r=.210$, $p>0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is hereby accepted. By this it means that there is no significant relationship between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State.

Discussion

Result from the study shows that about (77.5%) majority of the respondents have high level of knowledge of risky sexual behaviours. These finding corroborates the findings of, Asekun-Olarinmoye (2016) in her study on Parental attitudes and practice of sex education of children in Nigeria, the study found that majority (77.6%) of the adolescent girls had high level of knowledge towards sex education and its inclusion in their school curriculum. The findings of this study also show that females had some knowledge of contraceptives. Condoms were the most mentioned method of birth control.

The present study revealed that about (72.3%) of the respondents have positive attitude towards risky sexual behaviours while about (27.7%) have negative attitude. This finding is similar with the findings of Akokuwebe, Falayi, Adekola & Saliu (2019) who found that 87.8% of their respondents had positive attitude on risky sexual behaviours among adolescent. Asekun-Olarinmoye (2016), in her study on Parental attitudes and practice of sex education of children in Nigeria, found that majority of the parents had positive attitude towards sex education and its inclusion in the school curriculum of their children. Many of the respondents had basic knowledge of sex education, positive attitude and practiced it. The most common reason for non-practice was lack of skill.

It was also found that about (62.7%) majority of the respondents have positive perception towards risky sexual behaviours while about (37.3%) of the respondents have negative towards risky sexual behaviours. This result is consistent with the findings of Akpama (2017), in his study on Parental Perception of the Teaching of Sex Education to Adolescent in Secondary School in Cross River State, Nigeria, found that adolescent perception of the teaching of sex education to adolescents in secondary schools is significantly negative; no significant difference exists between literate and illiterate parents in their perception of the teaching of sex education to adolescents in secondary schools. It was concluded that parental perception of the teaching of sex education to adolescents in secondary schools is generally negative in Cross River State.

Furthermore, the result of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The correlation result table revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State ($r=.062$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is hereby rejected. By this it means that there is a significant relationship between knowledge level about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State.

Result from the study also revealed that there is no significant relationship between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. The correlation result table above revealed that there is a positive and an insignificant relationship between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State. ($r=.210$, $p>0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is hereby accepted. By this it means that there is no significant relationship between perception about risky sexual behaviours and risky sexual behaviours among adolescent girls attending Babcock university high school in Ilishan Remo, Ogun State.

Conclusion

Over the years the subject of sexuality and sex education has been a taboo in the school environment and the community. This lapses have caused some mishap on the society and as such instead of shying away from the topic of sexuality, this study concludes that schools and the society at large should engage in sex education programs with the aim of intimating the society on the subject matter. Parents also have a major role to play in disseminating the right information to their children on sexuality.

The study provided feedback on how students think and feel about sexuality education. Sexuality is a central aspect of being human. It encompasses gender, sex, identity and roles, pleasure, egotism, intimacy and reproduction. Sexuality is not only experienced physically but expressed in thought, desires, belief, fantasy, values, attitudes, behaviours, practices, roles and relationship. Secondly, condom education in sex education must be carefully handled as it may increase tendency for condom use among students as well as a marred perception of sexual behaviour. Consequently, the researcher is of the view that condom use in sex education should be de-emphasized and emphasizes placed on abstinence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. There is need for teachers to properly educate or inform students of the reason for the teaching of sex education in schools so as to eliminate wrong perceptions and or attitudes towards the subject.
2. The relevant government agencies in education must ensure that only professionally trained teachers are deployed in the classrooms to teach sex education so that its purpose will not be defeated.
3. There is the need for the Ministry of education in conjunction with other stakeholders to constantly review the existing sex education curriculum so that it can be more relevant to students in a fast-changing society.
4. Professionals need to be addressing expectations and assumptions concerning sexual intercourse, birth control, emotional impact, and physical aspect of intercourse with their clients, especially those who are younger and forming attitudes about sexual behaviours. Clients should have a clear understanding of how attitude can shape behaviour.
5. Schools need to be facilitating conversation with students in an effort to be aware of how cultural background impacts sexual attitudes and behaviours.
6. Schools need to be educating clients about how different sources of sexual knowledge can impact sexual attitude.

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